

Development and implementation of a public data repository for photovoltaic systems: Case study malta's living laboratories

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ABSTRACT

The transition to renewable energy, particularly Photovoltaic systems (PVs), is pivotal in achieving carbon neutrality goals. However, effective performance monitoring through data sharing remains challenging, especially in regions with unique environmental conditions. This study addresses these gaps by introducing Malta's first public data repository for PVs under the PROMISE project. The initiative integrates high-precision, laboratory-grade sensors compliant with IEC standards to ensure robust data acquisition and processing. The methodology builds on international best practices, employing advanced monitoring frameworks to capture meteorological and system parameters with high temporal resolution. Using three of the ten PV Living Laboratories in Malta, the system reflects typical installations in a Mediterranean Island Territory climate and the Maltese context. Data collection and processing adhere to European standards and established practices from existing public data repositories, ensuring compatibility and interoperability. By leveraging open-source platforms, the repository enables real-time visualization and the provision of structured historical datasets. Performance metrics, such as the DC performance ratio, are further employed to highlight the value of data sharing and collaboration in optimizing system performance and advancing predictive maintenance strategies. This work establishes a scalable framework for local PV monitoring and data sharing, advancing research and innovation in renewable energy and promoting Malta's participation in foreign programs. Future expansions aim to include additional laboratories, automate data uploads, and integrate Artificial intelligence (AI) driven fault detection tools, enhancing the system's utility and reliability.

1. Introduction

Renewable energy is widely recognized as the cornerstone of future energy generation, aligning with the European Union's ambitious goal of achieving carbon neutrality by 2050 [1]. Within this context, Photovoltaic systems (PVs) adoption has accelerated exponentially, driven by technological advancements, policy incentives, and the global push for sustainable energy solutions [2]. However, the need for comprehensive monitoring systems has grown significantly as PV systems become integral to the energy infrastructure.

Continuous monitoring throughout a system's lifecycle is essential to ensure optimal performance and address underperforming installations. This monitoring not only maximizes energy production but also provides critical insights into the impact of environmental conditions on

system efficiency and longevity. Studies have demonstrated that robust monitoring frameworks enhance the detection of faults, minimize downtime, and mitigate safety risks associated with malfunctioning components or external disruptions [3–7]. Monitoring is critical in assessing PVs degradation under diverse environmental conditions, especially in regions experiencing extreme temperatures, high humidity, or salinity. This process evaluates the performance of different PV technologies across various climatic zones and aids manufacturers in assigning performance ratio ratings tailored to specific climates. This approach is formalized as the "Climate Specific Energy Rating (CSER) in the International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC) 61,853–1, 2, 3, and 4 standards [8–11].

Many PVs rely on built-in commercial monitoring systems, usually featuring measuring equipment with lower accuracy classes. A recent

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study [12] has demonstrated that dedicated monitoring systems significantly outperform commercial alternatives in terms of accuracy and reliability, providing a more robust framework for detecting faults and optimizing performance. However, even with dedicated monitoring systems, data collection, sharing, and storage remain highly fragmented, often implemented on a case-by-case basis. This leads to further inconsistencies in data formats, measurement units, and distribution rights, undermining the potential of monitoring to deliver actionable insights. Such variability complicates efforts to build interoperable systems, hindering the development of predictive models, optimization tools, and grid management solutions, which are increasingly critical challenges as the PV industry expands.

Recognizing these challenges, several organizations in Europe have initiated efforts to address them by promoting standardized monitoring frameworks and centralized data systems. These efforts align with the principles of the European Data Strategy [13], which aims to create a single market for data, ensuring secure and standardized data sharing across sectors and borders. Initiatives such as the International Energy Agency (IEA) Photovoltaic Power Systems Programme (PVPS) Task 13 [5], Reliability and Performance of Photovoltaic Systems (PEARL PV) [14], and the Collaborative Platform for Simulation and Monitoring (COPLASIMON) [15] which have been developed under the European project Smooth, Reliable, and Dispatchable Integration of Photovoltaics (SERENDI-PV) [16] have been at the forefront, developing methodologies to harmonize data collection and improve system reliability. For instance, PVPS Task 13 focuses on enhancing the performance and reliability of PV systems by providing comprehensive guidelines for monitoring and data standardization. PEARL PV emphasizes the integration of operational data across European PV systems to study the effects of environmental conditions on performance, while COPLASIMON, under the SERENDI-PV project, leverages digital technologies like cloud computing, transfer protocols and data formats to address real-time monitoring and data sharing barriers. These collaborative efforts highlight the transformative potential of unified systems in advancing the PV industry, as highlighted in [17].

Despite these international program initiatives, Malta's PV community is still not contributing to this data-gathering and monitoring effort. Unlike other European regions, Malta's unique Mediterranean climate, classifying as Csa (Hot-summer Mediterranean climate) on the Koppen climate classification [18], and surrounded by the sea, is characterized by high temperatures, elevated humidity, and atmospheric salinity [19] presents challenges that demand tailored investigations. These environmental conditions accelerate PV system degradation, making comprehensive performance monitoring beneficial and essential.

As an island state, Malta represents a unique scenario with its 316 km² surface area [20], dense population of 1300 pp/km², and over 300,000 utility customers. It was also the first nation worldwide to adopt smart meters on a national level [21]. PV installations in Malta have reached 241.1 MWp, and almost 50 % of PV installations are from residential units with an average of 3.4 kWp, connected to their local Low Voltage (LV) network [22]. Given Malta's limited space, implementing robust PV monitoring systems is essential for optimizing the performance and reliability of installations and ensuring that the available land is used efficiently to maximize the generation of green, sustainable energy.

The limited existing practices for data gathering from installed PV systems are fragmented and often tailored for individual purposes, with limited or no data sharing among stakeholders. The challenges of fragmentation and tailored monitoring solutions remain an issue in Malta, hindering participation in international PVs monitoring programs. Therefore, this work aims to support the creation of Malta's first public data repository for PVs while considering Malta's specific environmental conditions and needs. The Photovoltaics Reliability Operations and Maintenance Innovative Solutions for Energy Alliance (PROMISE) project initiative aspires to offer an accessible platform of ten PV Living Laboratories [23], located as shown in Fig. 1, to facilitate data

Fig. 1. Malta PV living laboratories [28].

integration and advance PV research and development, enabling the development of predictive models and systems optimized for local island conditions. Towards this aim, the main objectives of this study are, therefore, to develop monitoring hardware and a software platform satisfying the following requirements:

- Utilize laboratory-grade, high-precision sensors (Grade A), as specified in the IEC 61,724-1 and 60,751 Standards for Class A monitoring [24].
- Incorporate all necessary meteorological and system parameters, ensuring compliance with IEC 61,724-1 Standard requirements for Class A monitoring [25].
- Install sensors following IEC 61,724-1 Standard methodology, following recommendations from PVPS Task 13 [5].
- Extract crucial performance metrics, enabling the monitoring of PV system performance and reliability, following guidelines from IEC 61,724-2 [26] and National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL) recommendations [27].
- Store data in a structured, standardized repository.
- Utilize a dedicated cloud platform for data upload and storage.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Section II reviews methodologies employed by international organizations for PV data collection, processing, sharing, and accessibility. Section III outlines the methodology adopted in this study, detailing data acquisition techniques and the implementation of data sharing through a public data repository while employing IEC standards to ensure data quality and integrity. Section IV presents the results and discusses their implications for PV performance and reliability. Finally, Section V concludes with a summary of key findings and suggestions for future work.

2. Pioneering frameworks for PV data collection and analysis

This section provides an overview of data repository platforms commonly used in PVs, highlighting the role of key research organizations and institutions in advancing data sharing and providing simulation tools. It also discusses related studies that have made their data publicly accessible, along with standard data collection, storage, and sharing practices. Key information, methodologies, and case studies are summarized in Table 1. Additionally, a universal data format template, currently in use to standardize data organization and ensure

Table 1
Studies using centralized data repositories.

Case studies	1	2	3	4
Reference	[37,38]	[39,40,42,43]	[35,44]	[43,45,46]
Project	Systems Integration Subprogram	Sole4PV	PVPS Task 13	SLTE/PV Lifetime
Lead Institution(s)	NREL	Sandia/PVPMC	IEA/Sandia	Sandia
Aim	Degradation Different climates	Performance models Real system data	Degradation Tropical climates with surrounding seas	PV temperature model Open source
Locations	Florida Oregon Colorado	New Mexico USA Denmark	Bangkok	New Mexico USA
Systems	3 1 system / site	6 3 systems / site	1	1
Period	2012–2014	2019–2020	2010–2018	2020 (1 year)
Meteorological Sensors	Pyronometers / Pyrheliometers GHI, DHI, DNI, G _{POA} Vaisala WXT520	Weather Station T _a , WS, RH	Reference cell G _{POA} Weather Station T _a , WS, WD, RH	Pyronometers G _{POA} Climatronic T _a , WS
System Systems	Class A DC parameters V _{DC} , I _{DC} , P _{DC} AC parameters V _{AC} , I _{AC} , P _{AC}	DC parameters V _{DC} , I _{DC} , P _{DC} Using voltage divider and manganin shunts AC parameters V _{AC} , I _{AC} , P _{AC}	DC parameters V _{DC} , I _{DC} , P _{DC} IV Curves AC parameters V _{AC} , I _{AC} , P _{AC}	DC parameters V _{DC} , I _{DC} , P _{DC} AC parameters V _{AC} , I _{AC} , P _{AC}
Sampling	Class A T _m : Omega CO1-T thermocouples 1 s	T _m : RTD sensor 10 ss	T _m : T-type thermocouples 30 ss	T _m : SA1-RTD-4W 1 or 5 ss
Repository	DuraMat	DuraMat PVPMC website	PVPMC website	DuraMat PVPMC website
Timesteps	5 to 15 min	Hourly	5 min	1 min

n.a. not available.

compatibility across research projects, is presented.

2.1. Background information

The Comprehensive Knowledge Archive Network (CKAN) is an open-source platform for effectively managing, organizing, and sharing datasets [29]. CKAN is not oriented toward a particular sector but is a versatile platform across various domains. Government institutions, research organizations, and private entities leverage CKAN for diverse applications, including open data initiatives, public service improvements, and collaborative research efforts. CKAN provides a structured approach to data management. Datasets can be cataloged with detailed metadata, including descriptions, tags, and licensing information, ensuring discoverability and standardization. CKAN's powerful search capabilities, data previews, and API integration facilitate seamless access and automation. Additionally, CKAN promotes collaboration by enabling multiple contributors to manage datasets within a unified system, making it particularly suited for large-scale research projects and public data repositories.

2.1.1. DuraMAT data hub

In the photovoltaic (PV) research community, CKAN's capabilities are exemplified by the Durable Module Materials Consortium (DuraMAT) Data Hub [30]. This cloud-based, open-source platform, hosted on CKAN, is dedicated to PV data sharing. DuraMAT facilitates data exchange between researchers, manufacturers, and other stakeholders. Unlike setting up an independent CKAN instance, which typically requires a physical or virtual server hosted on platforms such as Microsoft's Azure or Amazon Web Services (AWS), DuraMAT leverages a pre-established instance hosted on the servers of the National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL) [31]. This eliminates the need for individual users to manage server infrastructure, reducing costs and streamlining the data-sharing process. As a centralized repository, DuraMAT has become a widely used resource within the PV community for data dissemination and research.

Common research institutions and projects utilizing the DuraMAT Data Hub include the Photovoltaic Performance Modelling

Collaborative (PVPCM), the Photovoltaic Cell and Module Performance Evaluation Round-Robin (PVCAMPER) [32], the Sandia National Laboratories (Sandia) [33], and NREL. Additionally, other PV research initiatives, such as the Systems Long Term Evaluation (SLTE) [34], formerly PV Lifetime, share data through their websites while utilizing DuraMAT to ensure their data is still presented, standardized, and centralized. Notably, data from the PVPS Task 13 project is also made available on the PVPMC-Sandia website [35].

2.1.2. Other CKAN-Powered platforms

Beyond DuraMAT, other CKAN-powered platforms, such as PEARL PV and COPLASIMON projects, extend CKAN's utility to different contexts in PV research. PEARL PV, a network funded through the EU COST action framework, focuses on harmonizing data from European PV projects. This initiative aims to enhance collaboration among researchers and organizations while ensuring compliance with European research standards. By leveraging CKAN, PEARL PV provides a centralized interface for organizing and accessing datasets, enabling stakeholders to contribute and utilize data efficiently.

Similarly, COPLASIMON, developed under the Solar Energy Research, Enabling Digitalization for Photovoltaics (SERENDI-PV) project, leverages CKAN to facilitate data sharing, simulation, and monitoring. COPLASIMON enables researchers to contribute and access datasets, fostering collaboration within the PV community while also promoting reliable practices and harmonizing data collection methods [36].

2.2. Related studies with data sharing

2.2.1. Case 1

A study conducted at Cocoa, Florida (January 2011–March 2012), Eugene, Oregon (December 2012–January 2014), and Golden, Colorado (August 2012–September 2013) utilized advanced sensors to monitor photovoltaic (PV) module performance [37]. These PV systems represent system behavior in diverse climates, including subtropical (Cocoa), marine west coast (Eugene), and semi-arid (Golden). The primary aim was to gather high-quality data to validate and improve PV performance

models across varied environmental conditions and climatic regions.

I-V curve tracing was performed at intervals of 5 mins (Cocoa and Eugene) or 15 mins (Golden). Average power and back-of-module temperature were measured at 1-second intervals. Meteorological conditions, including Global Horizontal Irradiance (GHI), Diffuse Horizontal Irradiance (DHI), Direct Normal Irradiance (DNI), and Global Plane-Of-Array irradiance (G_{POA}), were sampled at 1-second intervals and averaged to 5-minute or 15-minute intervals, depending on the site. Sensors employed included Omega CO1-T thermocouples for back-surface temperature, Kipp & Zonen CMP22 pyranometers for G_{POA} and diffuse irradiance, Kipp & Zonen CHP1 pyrhemometers for DNI, and Vaisala WXT520 weather sensors for meteorological data. A data logger and Raven XE_EVDO communication devices facilitated data acquisition and processing. The resulting data, publicly accessible through the DuraMAT repository hosted on the CKAN platform, supports the validation and improvement of PV performance models [38]. NREL, Florida Solar Energy Center (FSEC), the University of Oregon, Sandia, and CFV Solar Test Laboratory were key contributors to this study.

2.2.2. Case 2

Data from monitored PVs in Albuquerque, New Mexico, and Roskilde, Denmark, consisting of multiple arrays, provided valuable benchmarks for evaluating PV performance models' accuracy, reliability, and variability using real-site data [39,40]. Data acquisition covered one year in Albuquerque (2020) and two years in Roskilde (2019–2020), with systems featuring diverse configurations, including monofacial and bifacial modules, fixed-tilt and tracking setups, and advanced PV technologies such as Panasonic HIT and Trina mono-PERC. These datasets, accompanied by comprehensive metadata such as system schematics, site details, and equipment photos, will continue to support advancements in PV performance modeling, foster collaboration, and enhance the reproducibility of research across diverse climatic conditions.

Irradiance levels were gathered using pyranometers for GHI, DHI, and G_{POA} irradiance and pyrhemometers for DNI. A weather station measured ambient temperature (T_a), relative humidity (RH), and wind speed (WS). Electrical parameters, such as DC power, voltage, and current, were captured using manganin shunts and voltage dividers. Class A meteorological sensors ensured high precision, while adherence to IEC 61,724 standards confirmed the high accuracy of electrical measurements. DC electrical sensor combiner boxes were installed at each inverter PV array, with AC outputs interfaced via AC electrical combiner boxes with each inverter. All Data were transmitted using the MODBUS RTU protocol (RS485) and aggregated in a Gantner QRC box for hourly processing. The schematic is available on [41]. Initial granularity for parameters such as GNI, DHI, and DNI was at 10-second intervals and averaged to hourly resolution for consistency with other measurements. All data were uploaded to cloud platforms through a Socotec gateway and made publicly available on the DuraMAT Data Hub [42] through the PVPDC Datasets website [43].

2.2.3. Case 3

Another system investigated by PVPS Task 13 between 2010 and 2018 was a free-standing flat roof PV grid-connected system consisting of 32 crystalline silicon modules arranged in two arrays [44]. The system is in a tropical, hot, and humid climate near the sea in southern Bangkok, Thailand. Installed in 2003, it includes half locally assembled and half imported PV modules.

This study aimed to assess the reliability and degradation of the 15-year-old system through annual visual inspections, electroluminescence imaging, and performance measurements, focusing on weather data, performance ratio, and module efficiency. The monitoring system recorded G_{POA} on a south-facing surface tilted at 14° , T_a using T-type thermocouples, WS, wind direction (WD), and RH. Electrical parameters included output DC voltage (V_{DC}) and current (I_{DC}) at the PV arrays, back-of-module temperature using T-type thermocouples, and inverter

output parameters such as utility grid AC voltage (V_{AC}) and current (I_{AC}), and Real Power (P_{AC}). The system adhered to the IEC 61724 standard for Class A monitoring systems, with precise meteorological instrumentation and high-frequency sampling at 30-second intervals. Data is available on the platform [35].

2.2.4. Case 4

The PV system monitored at Sandia in Albuquerque, New Mexico, was part of the SLTE project. Monitoring was conducted in 2020 over one year on panels installed in 2018 [45]. The primary goal was to validate PV module temperature prediction models by analyzing critical meteorological and system parameters affecting module temperature. Electrical parameters like V_{DC} and I_{DC} were recorded using high-precision Class A sensors adhering to IEC 61,724 standards, ensuring reliable measurements. Meteorological sensors employed included Kipp & Zonen CMP11 pyranometers for G_{POA} irradiance, cleaned biweekly to maintain accuracy; Climatronic 100093 aspirated shield sensors for ambient temperature with an accuracy of $\pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$ and Climatronic 102083 anemometers for wind speed, accurate to ± 0.11 m/s. Data were sampled at 1-second or 5-second intervals, averaged to 1-minute values for storage, and published in NetCDF format to facilitate efficient storage and retrieval. The data has been publicly available through the DuraMAT Data Hub [46] and the PVPDC Dataset website [43], supporting collaboration and further research in PV performance modeling.

2.3. Observations

These studies contribute significantly to the PV community; however, some significant monitoring details have not been reported. Specifically, information about acquisition and storage procedures, data transmission methods, and protocols would be beneficial. A monitoring system's accuracy relies heavily on its sensors' precision. Although the specifications and accuracy classes of meteorological sensors have been verified through model numbers and brands, limited details were provided regarding the electrical measurement parameters to establish their corresponding accuracy levels. The data uploaded and shared on the respective cloud platforms was presented with a granularity of 5 mins or more. These aspects have highlighted a demand from the public for finer data resolutions in future studies [39]. Furthermore, the study related to Case 2 provided data with inconsistent granularity: 5-minute intervals for Cocoa and Eugene and 15-minute intervals for Golden. This variation in granularity introduces differences in uncertainty levels across sites and complicates comparisons between them.

2.4. File and data format

PV communities commonly use structured formats like CSV (Comma Separated Variables) files for data storage and sharing in centralized repositories. These files include detailed headers for metadata, specifying parameters such as module identifiers, site location, time zone, latitude, and longitude, and module specifications such as tilt and azimuth angles. This metadata is provided in the first two rows of the file. The first row consists of nine standard field names with their corresponding descriptors in the second row. Table 2 provides the field positions and header information in rows 1 and 2 of the data file. Row 3 contains the header descriptors of each data column. The first column is always reserved for the measurement timestamp. In contrast, the subsequent columns contain the data according to the header descriptors, which generally consist of parameters like G_{POA} , T_m , V_{DC} , I_{DC} , V_{AC} , I_{AC} , P_{AC} , power factor (ϕ), Frequency (f), and meteorological conditions such as WS, T_a and RH.

Metadata includes geographic site data and specific measurement conditions to ensure traceability and usability. Quality control processes flag or replace missing data. Data is collected at high temporal resolutions and averaged to coarser intervals, such as one minute, for storage.

Table 2
Header file layout according to [38].

Field	Element (1st line)	Description (2nd line)
1	Module identifier	Unique identifier by the project
2	City	The City where the study was conducted
3	Country	The country where the study was conducted
4	Time zone	References from GMT
5	Latitude	In decimal degrees N, S
6	Longitude	In decimal degrees E, W
7	Elevation	Above sea level in meters
8	Module tilt	Module tilt for horizontal in degrees
9	Module Azimuth	PV module azimuth angle in degrees from north (N = 0, E = 90, S = 180, W = 270)

File naming conventions typically include site names and dataset characteristics for easy identification according to the ones referenced by the project. Timestamps follow the ISO 8601 format, ensuring consistency with universal time coordination (UTC).

3. Methodology

This section describes the first three labs of the Malta PV Living Laboratories platform, outlining their system specifications, monitoring parameters, and sensors used. The data collection and processing methodology and the data-sharing approach are explained in detail. Additionally, the method for identifying underperformance through the DC Performance Ratio (PR_{DC}), as defined by IEC 61724 standards, is presented to highlight some of the capabilities achieved through effective data sharing.

3.1. Malta PV living laboratories platform

The three rooftop PV systems described in Table 3 form part of The Malta PV Living Laboratories, a facility dedicated to collecting and analyzing data using holistic and open-source platforms. They were chosen to reflect typical small-scale installations with different technology product providers, configurations, and local operational environments. Table 3 provides an overview of the system specifications for each site, including the data capture periods, while Fig. 2 illustrates the 3 PV sites.

Table 3
Malta PV living laboratories platform multi sites under investigation.

	LAB 01	LAB 02	LAB 03
Geo-location	Central	Central	Central
Building Type	Terraced House	Residential (Public)	Semi-Detached Villa
System Type	Rooftop	Rooftop	Rooftop
Inverter Type	Central	Central	Central
Grid-Connected	Yes	Yes	Yes
Single/Three Ph	Single	Three	Single
Inverter	SMA SB1200	KOSTAL PLENTICORE Plus 10	SMA SB3000TL-21
Monitoring	No	No	Yes
Orientation	21°SW	26°SE	7°SW
Inclination	31°	15°	13°
Age (Years)	12	5	9
PV Modules (Wp)	IBC PolySol230TE	330	IBC PolySol260VL
Temp Coeff P_{MAX}	-0.44 (%/K)	-0.36 (%/K)	-0.39 (%/K)
Number of Panels	6	35	12
Rated (kWp)	1.380	11.550	3.120
Data Recordings	Jan-Nov 2024	Mar-Nov 2024	Mar-Nov 2024

3.2. Sensor and device selection

A fundamental aspect of data quality is the accuracy of the data acquisition system, particularly at the sensory layer. Table 4 summarizes the sensors' accuracy, key specifications, and parameters. The monitoring system employs high-precision electrical, meteorological, and irradiance sensors designed to capture data at 10-second intervals with exceptional accuracy and reliability. These laboratory-grade sensors operate on the Modbus RTU protocol via the RS485 wiring standard, ensuring cost-effective, scalable, and efficient data transmission.

The sensor accuracies are expressed as percentages, ranging from 0.2 % to 0.5 % for electrical measurements and 1.2 % for irradiance measurements with a temperature error of 0.4 % across an operating range of -35 °C to 80 °C, aligning well with Maltese climatic conditions. Temperature sensor accuracy was scaled at 1° Kelvin, while wind speed accuracy was 0.5 m/s or 5 %. The sensors are calibrated to Original Equipment Manufacturer (OEM) standards and certified under ISO 17025 and ISO 9001, ensuring precision and reliability. This compliance minimizes noise interference and facilitates the high-resolution measurements necessary for accurate analysis and real-time monitoring.

The accuracy thresholds classify all sensors as Class A, as defined by IEC 61724-1 [47] and IEC 60751 (2022) [24,48] Standards for RTD temperature sensors.

Measurements include a comprehensive range of meteorological and systems parameters critical to PV system performance. Systems parameters include Direct Current (I_{DC}), Direct Voltage (V_{DC}), Alternating Current (I_{AC}), Alternating Voltage (V_{AC}), Active Power (P_{AC}), Power Factor (ϕ), Reactive power (Q), Frequency (f) and Module Temperature (T_m). Meteorological parameters include Silicon Reference Cell for Global Plane-Of-Array (G_{POA}) irradiance, Reference Cell Temperature (T_{cell}), Ambient Temperature (T_a), and Wind Velocity (W_s). The DC Power (P_{DC}) is calculated by multiplying the I_{DC} and the V_{DC} measured by sensors. The aggregated DC power is also calculated for PV plants with multiple arrays. The accuracy level of these sensors and the range of measured parameters classify the monitoring system as Class A, as it meets the stringent requirements specified by IEC 61,724-1 for high accuracy. This approach ensures a reliable foundation for data quality and accuracy, which are essential for analysis, fault detection, and the calculation of key performance indicators, such as energy yields and performance ratios, in adherence to IEC 61,724-2 and IEC TS 61,724-3 standards [49].

3.3. Data acquisition, processing, and sharing framework

The data acquisition and processing framework for the Malta PV Living Laboratories is designed as a two-stage process. This approach minimizes the computational load on the Raspberry Pi by offloading tasks such as database hosting, data filtering, and numerical calculation to the server side. By focusing solely on data acquisition and communication, the Raspberry Pi avoids computational bottlenecks, ensuring robust real-time monitoring with minimal overhead.

3.3.1. Stage 1: real-time data acquisition and provisional cloud storage

Climatic conditions and cloud coverage on island nations like Malta transition faster than in mainland countries [50]. These rapid transitions necessitate capturing data at high granularity to ensure no significant environmental changes are overlooked. To account for these uncertainties, raw data is captured at 10-second intervals, enabling the system to monitor and respond to fast-changing weather patterns precisely. Data collection is managed by a Raspberry Pi, which acts as the controller device for the sensory layer and as an edge device to streamline communication between sensors and cloud platforms. Each sensor is assigned a unique identifier, and data is acquired using the Modbus RTU protocol over an RS485 wiring system. This setup ensures robustness and reliability by adhering to strict specifications, including baud rates, terminating resistors, and Modbus wiring standards, which

Fig. 2. Malta PV living laboratories, three sites under investigation from left to right: LAB01, LAB02 and LAB03.

Table 4
Summary of the sensors' technical specifications.

Parameter	Type	Accuracy	Range	Data transmission
V_{DC}	Voltage Sensor	0.5 %	0 to 800V _{DC} / 1200V _{DC}	Modbus
I_{DC}	Direct Current with CT through ModBus converter	0.2 % 0.1 %	0 - 40A _{DC}	Loop current Modbus
V_{AC} , I_{AC} , ϕ , f , P_{AC}	Single Phase Network Analyzer with for above 5A	0.5 %	various	Modbus
V_{AC} , I_{AC} , ϕ , f , P_{AC}	Three-Phase Network Analyzer with for above 5A	0.2 %	various	Modbus
G_{POA}	Reference cell with	IEC 61724 1.2 %	0 to 1500 Wm ⁻²	Modbus
T_{cell}	cell temperature	1 K	-40-+90 °C	
T_a	(inbuilt) ambient temp	IEC 60,751 - 1 K	0.9-40m/s	
WS	Pt1000 wind velocity	0.5m/s or 5 %		
T_m	module temp	IEC 60,751 - 1 K	-40-+90 °C	Modbus

minimize noise and transmission errors which are essential for the required accuracy. The Raspberry Pi operates on a Linux-based environment, and leverages open-source Python libraries for data acquisition, automation, and automatic real-time data uploads to cloud platforms such as Thingspeak [51] and Grafana Cloud [52]. This open-source approach provides flexibility while avoiding the costs of proprietary software. Raw data is autonomously uploaded to Thingspeak for data storage, while Grafana Cloud provides real-time data visualization through its dashboards. Grafana also offers minor processing capabilities, allowing DC power calculation and end users to visualize real-time performance metrics and detect underperformance issues, such as shading or faults, on the fly, enhancing system monitoring and operational reliability.

Remote access is enabled through RealVNC [53], allowing for system adjustments and troubleshooting post-deployment. This software and hardware architecture ensures the stability and scalability of the monitoring system, supporting long-term operational reliability with a high-level structure, as depicted in Fig. 3.

3.3.2. Stage 2: offline data processing, filtering, and public sharing

Periodically, raw data is manually downloaded from the cloud platform Thingspeak and imported for offline pre-processing, averaging, power calculations, and aggregation. To reduce dataset size while preserving essential resolution, the data is averaged into 30-second intervals, in alignment with the IEC 61724-1 standard. Preliminary

FRAMEWORK

Digital Sensor Device

Accuracy Class A (up to 0.5% error)

Digital Silicon Irradiance Sensor with Wind and Tamb [per system]

PV Module Temperatures [per array]

Pyrometers [Test Site Only]

Dust IQ [Test Site Only]

Energy/Power AC Meters/Analysers [per inverter]

DC Voltage Measurement [per array]

Analog Sensor Device

Accuracy Class A (up to 0.2% error)

DC Current Transducer [per array]

Fig. 3. Software and hardware architecture [28].

processing removes non-numeric values (NaNs) and outliers caused by system noise or interference. Statistical techniques such as high-resolution scatter plots and t -tests can effectively detect these anomalies. Scatter plots provide a visual representation of the relationship between variables, such as G_{POA} and I_{DC} , allowing the identification of outliers and patterns of deviation. Complementing this, t -tests can statistically evaluate the strength and significance of the relationship between these variables, ensuring the reliability of the data for subsequent analyses. The filtered and processed historical data and site-specific metadata are exported in CSV format and uploaded to the PV PROMISE project website. In addition to historical data, real-time raw data visualized through Grafana is publicly available on the same website.

3.4. Demonstrating a performance metric using the public data repository

Providing open access to data, users can evaluate PV module performances using metrics such as the performance ratio (PR_{DC}) and the normalized efficiency ($\eta_{N_{DC}}^{STC}$) [20] which is also known as the temperature-corrected performance ratio [20]. However, for this study, the focus is on the standard performance ratio. The calculation is by IEC TS 61724–2,3. The performance metric is implemented on LAB 1 from the Malta PV Living Laboratories, providing valuable visualization of PV system efficiency by evaluating the conversion of solar irradiance into usable DC energy under real-world conditions throughout the monitoring period. A daily plot identification method that detects underperformance issues is applied in LAB 3 by monitoring the actual and theoretical powers of the DC side of the PV system. Continuous monitoring of the performance metric enables the early detection of performance issues such as shading, soiling, or faults like power curtailments. By identifying inefficiencies through data acquisition, visualization, and monitoring, timely maintenance and optimization interventions can be performed to improve the system performance.

3.4.1. Data preparation and metrics implementation

The dataset used for this analysis contains measurements recorded at 30-second intervals, which are critical for calculating the performance metrics. These include:

- Global Plane-of-array (G_{POA}) irradiance
- DC power (P_{DC}): DC Voltage (V_{DC}) and DC Current (I_{DC}).
- Module temperature (T_m).

The GPOA values are acquired from a reference cell, which provides accurate results in scenarios requiring rapid responses to changes in irradiance, such as those commonly experienced on small islands such as Malta [50].

3.4.2. Performance ratio calculation

Eq. (1) calculates the performance ratio (PR), representing the overall effect of photovoltaic conversion. In this analysis, inverter and AC system losses are excluded to focus exclusively on the DC side of photovoltaic conversion.

$$PR_{DC} = \frac{Y_{DC}}{Y_r} = \frac{\int P_{DC} dt / P_{STC}}{\int G_{POA} dt / G_{STC}} \quad (1)$$

where, PR_{DC} represents the DC performance ratio, which is the DC system yield (Y_{DC}) ratio to the Reference Yield (Y_r). The DC system yield is defined as the measured DC energy produced by the PV modules (kilowatt hours) divided by the rated power of the PV array (P_{STC}) in kilowatts, which is the power of the system under Standard Test Conditions (STC) which assumes an irradiance of 1000 W/m^2 , (G_{STC}), a cell temperature of 25°C , T_{cell} and an Air Mass (AM) spectrum of 1.5. This term gives the number of hours of generation if the system was operating at the system's nominal power under STC. The reference yield Y_r is the plane-of-array insolation (kWh/m^2) divided by the reference irradiance

G_{STC} (1000 W/m^2). This signifies the number of hours in irradiance with a value of 1000 w/m^2 (G_{STC}).

3.4.3. Temporal aggregation and data filtering

Data from the repository is recorded at 30-second intervals, with DC power and solar irradiance integrated into one-hour periods for the data collection timeframe, which aligns with the method demonstrated. To maintain consistency, temperature measurements are also averaged over hourly intervals to align with the integrated energy data. Only data with irradiance values between 400 W/m^2 and 1200 W/m^2 were considered. This range complies with IEC TS 61,724–2:2016 standards [26] Class A monitoring systems specify irradiance thresholds within predefined limits, such as 0.4 to 1.2 Test Reference Condition (TRC). The choice of the lower threshold reflects a recent draft proposal recommending 400 W/m^2 as the minimum limit for accurate performance monitoring [54].

This methodology is particularly effective because it evaluates the performance ratio over short hourly timeframes, enabling the identification of uncertainties and performance variations during specific times of the day. Addressing issues at their source provides actionable insights into system behavior. In contrast, performance ratios calculated over more extended periods may highlight generalized underperformance but often fail to pinpoint localized or time-specific issues, potentially delaying corrective actions.

4. Data-Driven analysis and discussion

This section presents the results of three Malta PV Living Laboratories. Initially, it showcases the data repository system, followed by key plots extracted from the historical dataset and real-time visualizations from Grafana Cloud for LAB 01. Subsequently, it delves into the Performance Ratio (PR) visualization for LAB 01 and addresses the underperformance issues identified in LAB 03.

4.1. Public data repository

Time-series plots of all parameters are visualized on an interactive Grafana Cloud dashboard, shown in Fig. 4, generated using raw and real-time data with a resolution of 10 ss. The dashboard continuously updates the last 8000 data points, providing time-series visualizations covering the previous 24 h. Additionally, it includes site-specific and system-specific information. Grafana's built-in capabilities allow for simple data processing and the real-time computation of crucial performance metrics, such as DC powers and performance ratios. This functionality lets users detect underperformance issues, such as shading or faults, on the fly, facilitating system monitoring and operational reliability.

The historical file is exported as a CSV file and can be accessed through Malta PV Living Laboratories – PROMISE. Before the export, these files are processed to contain the metadata and headers, as discussed in section 2.4. All parameter values for LAB 01 are plotted with a temporal granularity of 30-second averages, representing two typical consecutive days in Malta, from October 31 to November 1, as shown in Figs. 5 and 6.

4.2. Performance analysis

Fig. 7 illustrates the performance metric of LAB 01 for one full year in hourly resolutions. Seasonal variations are evident, particularly during the summer when elevated ambient temperatures correspond to a rise in module and cell temperatures. These increases result in a significant reduction in the PR, highlighting its expected sensitivity to temperature fluctuations.

A noteworthy observation emerges from the monitoring period before May for LAB 03, as shown in Fig. 8 (left plot). Based on irradiance data, this plot shows a substantial discrepancy between the expected and

Fig. 4. Real-time visualization of LAB 01 through Grafana Cloud.

Fig. 5. Electrical and meteorological parameters vs time.

Fig. 6. Electrical generation/theoretical/ vs time.

Fig. 7. LAB 1 hourly performance ratio with ambient temperature vs time.

Fig. 8. LAB 3 left: Power curtailment issue, right: normal operating conditions.

actual power generation. This discrepancy, particularly evident during peak daylight hours, accounts for the low-performance ratios observed during these times. Investigations revealed that these discrepancies were caused by power curtailment due to overvoltage issues on the low-voltage (LV) grid. This resulted in 34.59 % downtime and a loss of over 7.4 kWh from an expected energy yield of 15.67 kWh. The power curtailment rectification from May onwards led to a marked improvement in the PR, as also evidenced by Fig. 8 (right plot), which demonstrates a stabilized voltage level in compliance with EN 50160 Standards [55,56].

5. Conclusions

This study has successfully introduced a framework to facilitate data sharing through a public repository system. The application of various monitoring techniques to the shared data has revealed under-performance issues, which have led to the resolution of the issue on LAB 03. This initiative adds value to the PV community by promoting transparency and collaboration. It also encourages stakeholders, manufacturers, and the public to understand PV system behavior in diverse environments, enhancing future development through research. Additionally, it serves as a hub for research and innovation, aiding Malta's participation in international programs.

By providing open access to data, users can evaluate PV module performance using metrics such as the Performance Ratio. The data from the first three laboratories of the Malta PV Living Laboratories is now publicly accessible. This repository is expected to be expanded to include seven additional laboratories and a testing site. This expansion aims to enhance the richness of our dataset, providing valuable insights into PV system performance across diverse environments to the PV community and beyond.

The granularity of data plays a crucial role in accurately assessing PV system performance. High-resolution data enables the detection of transient events and subtle performance issues that may be overlooked with coarser datasets. For instance, detailed monitoring can identify rapid fluctuations in irradiance or temperature, which is essential for precise performance analysis and fault detection. Studies have shown that increased data granularity improves the accuracy of performance

assessments and fault detection in PV systems.

In contrast, studies with lower data granularity may miss short-term variations and anomalies, leading to less accurate performance evaluations. Our approach distinguishes us from other studies by providing high-resolution data, offering a more detailed and accurate understanding of the PV system behavior. This level of detail supports more effective analysis, maintenance, and optimization of PV installations, ultimately contributing to the advancement of photovoltaic technology and its applications.

5.1. Future projections

Historical data is downloaded and uploaded manually at periodic intervals, which can be time-consuming and prone to errors. To enhance efficiency and streamline operations, we plan to automate this process in the future. Automated downloads and uploads will minimize manual intervention, reduce errors, and improve data accuracy, optimizing our data management workflow.

Our plans include developing and deploying AI-powered dynamic fault detection and performance assessment tools tailored to our PV systems. This initiative aims to automate the identification of anomalies, assess their impact on performance, and recommend corrective actions, thereby enhancing the overall reliability and efficiency of PV installations. By embracing AI technologies, we are committed to advancing our system's fault detection and diagnosis capabilities, ensuring higher efficiency and reliability in our photovoltaic systems while publicly sharing the knowledge and data with the PV community. Overall, the framework developed in this research offers a scalable and adaptable solution for improving the efficiency and reliability of PV systems, particularly in regions like Malta, where environmental and grid-related challenges are prominent. Future research will focus on expanding this framework to encompass additional variables and exploring the broader applications of the findings to other regions with similar environmental conditions.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Brian Bartolo: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft,

Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Brian Azzopardi**: Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Kenneth Scerri**: Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources.

Declaration of competing interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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